

Learning from Long-Term Care practices
for the European Care Strategy

NATIONAL REPORT DENMARK:

The meanings of LTC work and quality of LTC work
in Denmark

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The meanings of LTC work and quality of LTC work in Denmark

Brief summary

There is no single definition on what the meaning of LTC work is, however pointing towards that it relates to different types of work related to supporting especially elderly people either in their private home or at an institution. Quality of LTC work relates to the issue of the ability to have the necessary staff and time to deliver the long-term care work for the professionals doing the work in the sector, as well as the level of wages.

1, Introduction and definitions

There is no common and clear description of what LTC work is, however, it refers typically to those working within what is seen as the long-term care sector, e.g. support in private homes as well as within long-term care institutions. In this way it seemingly follows the OECD definition that “LTC workers are individuals who provide care to recipients at home or in LTC institution (other than hospitals). Following the OECD definition, formal LTC workers comprise two main professional categories: nurses and personal care workers. Personal care workers include formal workers providing LTC services at home or in institutions (other than hospitals) and who are not qualified or certified as nurses“ (*Who Cares? Attracting and Retaining Elderly Care Workers 2020*, 68). In Denmark the main group of professions working with LTC are Social and health care assistants and Social and health care supporters. Additionally, nurses, occupational therapist and physiotherapists are among the LTC workforce. (Kommunernes Landsforening 2023). The difference in tasks between assistant and supporter is that the former have more responsibilities including co-ordination and planning, whereas the supporters do a large and varied number of practical types of work within the sector. There is also a difference in the length of the education. Recent years have seen more staff such as physiotherapists and occupational therapists become part of the support for being able to live independently (Indenrigs- og Sundhedsministeriets Benchmarkingenhed 2024).

The content of work relates to all types of tasks within the long-term care sector, ranging from practical help to more specialised personal care and support.

2. Boundaries, Differentiation, Interrelations

There are no clear boundaries between formal and informal work, especially with regard to issues related to support in private homes, given that support with issues such as cleaning, cooking and shopping as well as other practical tasks can also be done through informal support from a partner, friend or family member. Re-enablement and personal care, however, can to a lesser extent be done by informal support. More specialised issues related to health is done by nurses or referral to the health care sector. Social care workers are the largest employed group of workers within long-term care in Denmark.

The level of education varies, ranging from professionals to unskilled. The formal education is state based and with education, for example, as nurses and social assistants. Occupational therapists and physiotherapists are also formal state educations. There is a growing discussion about whether there is sufficient qualified staff to do the work within the sector. It is a labour force mainly consisting of women. There is an increasing share of people with another ethnic background employed within the sector. There has been an increase in the number of LTC staff employed overall (Kommunernes Landsforening, 2023).

The daily working conditions within the field are regulated by the municipalities, e.g. such as when one has to work night and day. The wage and other work issues are part of collective agreements as is the tradition within the Danish labour market. There is an overall framework for all workers within municipalities with some specific differences depending on what certain groups have asked for, this can be a difference in basic salary and compensation for working during nights and weekends. State and EU regulations of safety at work, working times rules etc. naturally also apply to this field of work.

Overall, the content of long-term care work is not a central issue regarding long-term care policy in Denmark, instead it is the level and quality of support of the work and the quality of work, see also later, that are the central issues. This with the exception of a worry concerning lack of qualified staff now and in the future.

3. Resources, Infrastructure, Regulation

There is information on the number of persons employed within different parts of the LTC sector, see Table 1. This is register based data and covers public as well as the limited number of employed as private providers.

Tabel 1: Employed within LTC in 2022

Units: Number

	Total	Men	Women
871010 Nursing homes	72201	6517	65684
871020 Residential nursing care facilities	4528	477	4051
873020 Sheltered dwellings, etc.	477	93	384
881010 Home help	54580	7837	46743

Source: www.statistikbanken.dk/RAS309

There are information and options to get information on more specific groups employed in the public sector (Kommunernes Landsforening, 2023), albeit not very detailed. The information herein is provided also as this gives insight to the collective negotiation of wages in order to be able to estimate cost of change in wage costs. Thus, costs related to doing the care work is also an important issue.

In 2023 there were 61.000 social care workers employed of which 10.300 were without a formal education. There were 10.500 nurses, 1400 occupational therapists and 800 physiotherapists employed in the municipalities (Social, Bolig og Ældreministeriet, 2024). There has been an increase in the number without formal education since 2018, where it was 4.900. There is variation across municipalities in the number of staff without formal qualifications. It has further to be borne in mind

that a number of those without formal education are expected to, at some point, totake a formal education within the field (Indenrigs- og Sundhedsministeriet Benchmarkingsenhed 2024).

It is possible to get information on employed in municipalities (<https://www.krl.dk/#/sirka>), albeit the number of employed and their wages alone do not give a lot of information as it will depend on the demographic and socioeconomic situation in the different municipalities. There is no central information on the cost related to the training of employed staff, which is the responsibility of each municipality.

Overall, there has been an increase in the number of employed within long-term care in the municipalities. One caveat being that due to COVID19 data in these years might be blurred by the extra tasks related hereto.

Again, the main issue is how to ensure that there will be sufficient staff in the future, and what options there will be to do so and under what conditions.

4. Stakeholders and Governance

Central stakeholders are the municipalities who have the responsibility for long-term care, and this in dialogue with users as many municipalities have an elderly council. Additionally, and despite it is without formal rights to decide, they can be in dialogue with decision-makers. There is also co-ordination with trade unions shop stewards as the one to discuss organisation and local working conditions with.

The overall framework with regard to wages are negotiated by Kommunernes Landsforening (KL - Local Government Denmark) with the different trade-unions within long-term care with FOA as a central organisation. Albeit the collective agreements often imply that the general changes in wages, working time etc is typically done for all groups in the public sector, including the municipalities, at the same time. Still, there are negotiations of specific working conditions for those within the LTC sector when there are negotiations of renewal of the collective agreements.

Social protection for the employed is, as in other parts of the Danish Welfare State, universal in approach, e.g. decided centrally. The exception is that an individual will have to be member and pay a contribution to the unemployment insurance. A further exception is that collective agreements typically imply that workers have full income during sickness, leave (birth of a child) as well as saving for pension purposes as part of the occupational welfare in the Danish welfare state. There can be a variation in some fringe benefits across municipalities. Thus, there can be variation in working conditions.

This at the same time also highlights the issue that informal workers (typically without formal contracts or working in the hidden economy), or those delivering work via platforms (such as cleaning work) and are considered self-employed have less coverages in case of sickness, pension savings as well as holidays (Behrendt, Nguyen, and Rani 2019; Palier 2019; Greve 2019).

Overall, the central level has less responsibility except with regard to the overall framework of the legal rights and options available for the local municipalities and their economic opportunities.

Central tension is related to the quality of work, see later, and the remuneration of work within the sector as well as how to ensure that the necessary qualified staff will be available in the years to come.

5. Quality of care work

One of the issues concerning the quality of work relates to the ability of having the necessary staff being able to deliver the long-term care work. Overall, this is due to a general work shortage, but also due to the need of different kinds of staff. Long-term care jobs in Denmark are, as described earlier, of different kind. There is no specific definition of what long-term care workers are, but social care workers with an education are a central group in the local work. Besides this there are also nurses for the specific health care issues, and as a consequence of the lack of educated workers there are also unskilled persons supporting the long-term care work in Denmark. Informal care is recognised and expected for persons living together, albeit there is no detailed information on the extent. However, some indicators may be when grown up children do care work for their parents which in turn may influence their working time on their job.

One of the elements of quality of work might be how the working conditions influence long-term care workers, including having to work at times not fitting well with family life, but also heavy lifting and a professional feeling of not being able to deliver what the professionals find is important can have an impact (Indenrigs- og Sundhedsministeriets Benchmarkingenhed 2024). Here it looks like increased responsibility and stronger relations with the users can be one of the issues to pursue, as an evaluation of teams in 25 different municipalities indicated that this was the case (Buch and Topholm 2024). This might also imply that better working conditions can be related to sustainability of available working staff. In relation to this, several of the stakeholders in our interviews mentioned flexibility in working hours, recognition and wages as indicators which, in their opinion, could improve the working conditions.

Looking at the quality of work revolves in Denmark, like also internationally (OECD 2023; Eurofound 2020), to revolve around issues like the level of wages, working hours (including the issue of nights and weekends) as well as possible strain of working within the sector. This might be different between home care and institutional care, also given that elderly in institutions need support 24 hours a day, whereas home care is often during daytime (except for those in need for frequent visits to cope with personal care). There is in Denmark, as other countries, a number of physical as well as mental/health risks for the long-term care workers. There might be different strategies at stake to cope with these, including using welfare technology, such as a way of reducing heavy lifting (B. Greve 2016).

In Denmark one issue to increase the recognition of care workers has, according to OECD 2023, p. 131, been a recognition of experience in education and training. The recognition of the value of the jobs is also an important issue. This was also mentioned in our interviews with stakeholders, where one stakeholder for example stated that a way of showing recognition is related to wages: "There is a recognition agenda, which for example also involves salary. Is this a job I can live off? And where I feel that my effort is commensurate with what I get paid, and in comparison to what other people in society get paid

The perceived meaningfulness of the work seems to have a positive impact on quality of work within long-term care (Eurofound 2020). Several of our stakeholder mentioned this in our interviews as a motivation for people working with long-term care: "The fantastic thing about our area is that it consists of people who find great meaning in helping others. I was about to say that what drives our

employees, and what I experience, is that they find great meaning in working with other people. The whole aspect of relation work and caregiving, helping others in need, gives them a great sense of purpose."

The meaningfulness of the work was thus discussed among stakeholders, however mainly in relation to the ability to attract workers in the future, and thus only more indirectly in relation to the quality of work.

The content of the work and the employees' influence on their work is also argued to be a quality of work element (Pedersen 2024), and this was confirmed during the interview especially with the different municipalities interviewed. This will be elaborated in the following section.

An issue regarding informal care is the risk that this might not necessarily continue, e.g. the classical voluntary failure (Salamon 1987) and furthermore, not all persons will be able to do informal care. It is seen as an issue that some, but not all, will have access to informal care, while at the same time decisions on support with practical and other services in private homes do take into consideration whether and how an individual might be supported especially by those they are living with.

6. Current debates

The primary focus in the current debates is on the issues mentioned in the Section above. However, further as an issue that might influence the ability of attracting the necessary level of staff in the future, as well as there can be a risk of that fewer young people enter education important can influence the ability to get the necessary qualified staff in the future.

In Denmark long-term workers are by now in many municipalities being organized in teams, with one of the aims being to give the long-term worker more influence on the daily work. The fact that the workers get more influence in their workday was welcomed positively by stakeholders in several of our interviews. It was furthermore discussed the possible consequence of the new legislation from 2025 where user is expected to have more influence on what to do. It was stated in some of the interviews that one important factor in the quality-of-care work is the long-term care worker's professional competences, and that it is important for the workers to get to use these in order to feel content with their working lives. With the new initiative some are afraid that the professionalism will

be second to the long-term care user's wishes: "They are also very focused on the professional competences, so they also have an expectation that the healthcare effort should mean something, should play a significant role in elderly care. And that it is used actively, so I also think they have an expectation that their professionalism should be utilized, and that it's not just about drinking coffee."

The level of wages and how this have an impact on the qualified staff employed can also be considered an issue. As mentioned earlier this was confirmed in our interviews with stakeholders.

Literature

- Behrendt, Christina, Quynh Anh Nguyen, and Uma Rani. 2019. 'Social Protection Systems and the Future of Work: Ensuring Social Security for Digital Platform Workers'. *International Social Security Review* 72 (3): 17–41.
- Buch, Martin Sandberg, and Emmy Hjort-Enemark Topholm. 2024. 'Faste, Tværfaglige Og Selvstyrende Teams i Ældreplejen—Erfaringer Fra 25 Kommuner'. København.
- Eurofound. 2020. 'Long Term Care Workforce: Employment and Working Conditions-L'. *Long Term Care Workforce: Employment and Working Conditions*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/fr/publications/2020/long-term-care-workforce-employment-and-working-conditions>.
- Greve, B. 2016. *Long-Term Care for the Elderly in Europe: Development and Prospects*. Edited by B. Greve. *Long-Term Care for the Elderly in Europe: Development and Prospects*. 1st ed. Oxon: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315592947>.
- Greve, Bent. 2019. 'The Digital Economy and the Future of European Welfare States'. *International Social Security Review* 72 (3): 79–94.
- Indenrigs- og Sundhedsministeriets Benchmarkingenhed. 2024. 'Kommunernes Arbejde Med Fastholdelse Af Social- Og Sundhedspersonalet På Ældreområdet.' København. <https://www.benchmark.dk/Media/638532548913017418/Hovedrapport%20-%20Kommuners%20arbejde%20med%20fastholdelse%20af%20social-%20og%20sundhedspersonale%20p%c3%a5%20%c3%a6ldreomr%c3%a5det.pdf>.
- Kommunernes Landsforening. 2023. 'Det Kommunale Arbejdsmarked i Tal 2022'. København. ISBN 978-87-93950-98-6-pdf.
- OECD 2020. *Who Cares? Attracting and Retaining Elderly Care Workers*. 2020. OECD Health Policy Studies. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/92c0ef68-en>.
- OECD. 2023. 'Beyond Applause? Improving Working Conditions in Long-Term Care: An Overview'. Paris: OECD.
- Palier, Bruno. 2019. 'Work, Social Protection and the Middle Classes: What Future in the Digital Age?' *International Social Security Review* 72 (3): 113–33. <https://doi.org/10.1111/issr.12218>.

Pedersen, Maria Hjortsø. 2024. *Implementeringen Af Selvstyrende Teams i Ældreplejen: Et Studie Af Nye Styringsformer Og Omsorgspraksisser*. Roskilde: Roskilde Universitet.

Salamon, Lester M. 1987. 'Of Market Failure, Voluntary Failure, and Third-Party Government: Toward a Theory of Government-Nonprofit Relations in the Modern Welfare State'. *Journal of Voluntary Action Research* 16 (1–2): 29–49.